

IMPROVED TRANSDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE
FOR EFFECTIVE ECOSYSTEM-BASED
MARITIME SPATIAL PLANNING AND
CONSERVATION IN EUROPEAN SEAS

Deliverable D6.3

Public, open-source release of any
modifications made to the EwE software

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MARINEPLAN PROJECT SUMMARY

The diversity of terrestrial and marine life is dramatically affected by human interventions including climate change. Compelling and growing evidence shows that biodiversity underpins ecosystem functions and services, and consequently human benefits depending on them. Thus, the importance of ecosystems in a good state cannot be underestimated and calls for an effective management of marine activities and sustainable use of marine and coastal resources.

Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) is the main governance process that ideally balances economic, ecological and socio-cultural goals through the regulation of human uses at sea. With the global and regional conservation and green energy targets ahead, there is an urgent need to define pathways for a better alignment of MSP and strategic conservation planning, as part of the operationalisation of an Ecosystem-Based approach to MSP (EB-MSP).

The EU-funded MarinePlan project supports the implementation of EB-MSP through the development of a Decision Support System (DSS). It will offer guidance for an improved alignment of MSP, spatial conservation, and restoration interventions during the challenging times of ever-increasing pressures on marine ecosystems.

This main goal will be achieved through four specific objectives for the European seas:

- #1 Co-develop with stakeholders the conceptual elements of the DSS (guidelines and tools) and derive best practice guidance for EB-MSP implementation.
- #2 Develop quantitative metrics to operationalise Ecologically or Biologically Significant marine Area (EBSA) criteria and their application at various spatio-temporal scales.
- #3 Implement and apply the DSS based on objectives #1 and #2, its guidelines, metrics and tools at Planning Sites representing the diversity of European marine areas.
- #4 Provide recommendations and improvements concerning the shortcomings, impediments to and opportunities of prevailing governance processes to enhance the implementation of EB-MSP.

MarinePlan develops and applies the EB-MSP DSS within seven Work Packages and eight European Planning Sites. The Planning Sites range from coastal ecosystems to open ocean and the deep sea and from local to transboundary scales. Applying and validating the DSS incorporates realistic planning scenarios, key action points to achieve the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and policy recommendations on how to enhance EB-MSP implementation in European Seas. MarinePlan will communicate results to decision-makers at horizontal (between sectors) and vertical (from local to European) levels and enable the transfer of knowledge to areas in differing socio-ecological settings. The improved natural and social science base will ensure effective policymaking to support a greater coherence in implementing environmental policies as well as to enable streamlined planning for marine industries.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MarinePlan project features the application of the Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) food web modelling approach to specific Planning Sites, most notably in the northwestern Mediterranean. Ecopath International Initiative, the development hub of the EwE approach has been tasked with the execution and customisation of the EwE ecosystem modelling approach where necessary, and to make any modifications and repairs to the software publicly available.

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1 AIM OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable summarizes relevant changes made to the free and open-source EwE approach under MarinePlan.

1.1 CONTRIBUTORS

Table 1. Names and roles of contributors to this deliverable.

Name	Affiliation	WP Lead	Task Lead
Marta Coll	ICM-CSIC	Researcher	

2 INTRODUCTION

The MarinePlan project addresses the need for a cohesive and adaptive EB-MSP framework that aims at helping member states to fulfil the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Against this background, MarinePlan develops a DSS equipped with tools and guidelines for reconciling conservation and restoration measures with national and transnational MSP applications. A fundamental aspect of this DSS is an undervalued but essential component to explore the potential effectiveness of spatial planning, systematic conservation planning and ecosystem restoration: marine ecosystem modelling.

Marine Ecosystem Models or MEMs are complex, mechanistic approaches that help improve understanding the workings of and dynamics within marine food webs and the influences of human activities and environmental change (Steenbeek et al., 2024). The modelling involved integrates a wide range of disciplines, including physical oceanography, biochemistry, food web dynamics, human activities, and risk analysis (Figure 1). An Achilles heel of formal planning procedures such as Marine Spatial Planning and Systematic Conservation Planning is that they rely on spatial optimizations of status quo, without being able to explore the future effectiveness of optimized planning options. Here, MEMs can make an invaluable contribution to the MarinePlan EB-MSP framework: they offer the ability to explore, with associated uncertainty, how the future ecosystem may respond to scenarios of fisheries management and human uses of the marine space, in the context of changing climates.

Figure 1 - The interconnected pressures, processes and ecosystem services that Marine Ecosystem Models typically consider

The MEM software that was selected for MarinePlan is Ecosim (Christensen and Walters, 2004; de Mutsert et al., 2024), a free and open-source modelling approach built by and for scientists under the auspices of Ecosim International Initiative (WP6 leads), supported by a global network of researchers and the Ecosim Research and Development Consortium.

To support the application of the EwE approach for relevant Planning Sites, MarinePlan Task 6.4 allotted budget to make software repairs and extend the software's capabilities where needed. In accordance to its open-source software license, any modification made to the EwE software must be made publicly available.

3 ECOPATH WITH ECOSIM (EwE) – A BRIEF OVERVIEW

Ecopath with Ecosim or EwE is an ecological model that tracks the paths of energy through a food web. The food web is defined through the concept of functional groups, which can represent a single species, an aggregation of species with similar ecological roles, or a life stage of a single species. The EwE approach unifies ecological cascades, the impacts of fishing and environmental change in an open parameterizable set of generic equations that can be used to represent any ecosystem (Christensen and Walters, 2004; Heymans et al., 2016).

EwE contains three main modules:

3.1 ECOPATH

The foundation of the EwE approach is Ecopath, is a mass-balanced model that represents a snapshot of the energy flows within a food web (Christensen and Pauly, 1992; Polovina, 1984). The Ecopath model defines the structure of the food web, any exploitation, and the quantified predator-prey relationships within the food web. By accounting for all the energy flows into, through, and out of the ecosystem, Ecopath captures create a mass-balanced mathematical representation of the ecosystem (Christensen and Pauly, 1992).

Ecopath uses a system of linear equations to describe the energy flows between functional groups over a period of time, typically a year, which can be summarized as follows (Eq. 1):

$$B_i \cdot \left(\frac{P}{B}\right)_j = \sum B_j \cdot \left(\frac{Q}{B}\right)_j \cdot DC_{ji} + BA_i + E_i + Y_i + B_i \cdot \left(\frac{P}{B}\right)_i \cdot (1 - EE_i) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where, for functional groups i and j , B is biomass; P/B is production per unit of biomass; BA is biomass accumulation rate; E is net migration rate (emigration – immigration); Y is total fishery catch (yield) rate; EE is ‘ecotrophic efficiency’, defined as the proportion of the production that is utilized in the system; Q/B is consumption per unit of biomass; and DC_{ji} the fraction of prey i in the diet of predator j . The term $(1 - EE_i)$ is also referred to as MO , unexplained mortality.

For each group, Ecopath requires input values for B , Q/B , P/B , DC , Y , and other values are optional. Of B , P/B , Q/B , and EE , three values must be entered while the fourth will be estimated by the model (Christensen and Pauly, 1992; Christensen and Walters, 2004). The Ecopath input parameters are based on standard stock assessments and are often readily available.

3.2 ECOSIM

The temporal module of EwE, Ecosim, runs the Ecopath base model over time. By providing the software with historical trends in environmental change, primary productivity, and fisheries, Ecosim replicates past trends in the ecosystem to understand historical ecosystem dynamics, onto which explorations of plausible future conditions can be explored (Ahrens et al., 2012; Christensen and Walters, 2004).

To do so, Ecosim augments the mass-balanced Ecopath parameter set with additional parameters related to behaviour and temporal dynamics, and applies these to a series of time-dependent differential equations, expressing the biomass growth rate as (Eq. 2):

$$\frac{dB_i}{dt} = g_i \cdot \sum Q_{ji} - \sum Q_{ij} + I_{ji} - (M_i + F_i + e_i)_i \cdot B_i \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where, for functional groups i and j , dB/dt represents growth rate during time interval dt ; g is net food conversion efficiency (P/Q); I is immigration rate; M is natural mortality rate; F is fishing mortality rate; e is emigration rate.

Ecosim stabilizes its food web dynamics through the concept of the foraging arena, which expresses that through predator avoidance behaviour, at any given moment in time, only a fraction of a total prey biomass is vulnerable to predation by a predator (Ahrens et al., 2012).

In its simplest form, the consumption rate is defined as (Eq. 3):

$$Q_{ij}(B_i, B_j) = \frac{v_{ij} \cdot a_{ij} \cdot B_i \cdot B_j}{v'_{ij} + v_{ij} + a_{ij} \cdot B_j} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where, for prey group i and predator j , Q is consumption; B is biomass; a is effective search rate; v is vulnerability to predation exchange rate; and v' is invulnerable to predation exchange rate. The foraging area concept implies that predators, over time, may greatly vary the composition their diets with fluctuations of available prey.

3.3 ECOSPACE

The third main component of EwE is Ecospace, a spatiotemporal-explicit module that extends the Ecosim parameter set with extra parameters related to spatial preferences and movement. Ecospace represents the modelled area as a two-dimensional grid of equally sized cells in which fisheries and functional groups interact and gravitate towards more favourable conditions according to modified versions of the Ecosim differential equations (de Mutsert et al., 2024; Walters et al., 1999).

Grid cells can be blocked out from having ecosystem dynamics to represent land (for marine ecosystems) or cells that fall beyond the modelled area of interest.

3.3.1 Species dynamics

Ecospace contains a highly configurable niche model that defines cell suitability for functional groups. Central to this concept is the term of 'capacity', or 'habitat foraging capacity' in full, which defines the suitability of functional groups to forage across the spatial grid (Christensen et al., 2014). Ecospace affects the capacity of a predator to forage as follows (Eq. 4):

$$V = \frac{vB}{v + v' + aP/A} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where, for a given predator, V is vulnerable prey density; B is prey biomass, P is predator abundance; v and v' are vulnerability exchange rates to and from the feeding arena; a is search rate; and A is the foraging arena size.

The HCFM niche model can derive the foraging capacity via combining hypotheses related to:

- The spatial distribution of habitats (or substrate types) and the preference of a given functional group for each habitat type.
- The spatial distribution of relevant environmental parameters and the preference for / tolerance to a given functional group to a specific environmental driver.
- Through external forcing, in case an external species distribution model is used.

Ch is defined as the total suitability of a cell for a species to feed in due to the presence of preferred habitats (Eq. 5):

$$Ch_i = \sum_{h=1}^n r_h \cdot p_{i,h}; \quad Ch_i \in [0, 1]; r_h \in [0, 1]; p_{i,h} \in [0, 1] \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where, for functional group i and habitat h , Ch is habitat capacity; n is the number of habitats; r is the ratio of the cell area covered by a habitat; p is habitat preference of a group to a specific habitat.

Environmental capacity of a cell Ce , on the other hand, is defined as the multiplicative assessment of environmental preferences (Eq. 6):

$$Ce_i = \prod_{e=1}^m Y_{i,e}; \quad Ce_i \in [0, 1] \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where, for functional group i and environmental driver e , Ce is environmental capacity; m is the number of environmental drivers, and Y is the environmental preference of group i to environmental condition e as dynamically evaluated across the spatial grid (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Schematic representation of the environmental capacity calculations with 4 hypothetical environmental preference functions. Environmental suitability Y for environmental driver e is obtained by looking up cell value X along environmental preference function F . The total environmental suitability for a cell is then defined as $Y1 \cdot Y2 \cdot Y3 \cdot Y4$ (adapted from Christensen et al., 2014)

The total capacity C_i in a cell for a functional group is then simply defined as (Eq. 7):

$$C_i = Ch_i \cdot Ce_i; \quad Ce_i \in [0, 1] \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

Note that EwE release 6.5 introduces the flexibility to derive capacity from habitats alone (Eq. 4), from environmental responses alone (Eq. 5), or from both (Eq. 6). This is a per-group setting.

Functional groups in Ecospace will gravitate towards better nearby conditions, with better feeding opportunities and lower risk to predation. A set of specific parameters controls functional group movement: dispersal (average distance a group moves, during the Ecopath period, while searching for food), advection (current-induced movement), and migration (directed behavioural movement patterns) (de Mutsert et al., 2024). Groups can also be coaxed to stay out of ‘bad’ habitat, where risk to predation can be higher, and increased movement rates serve to return to more suitable habitat. Ecospace considers a cell as bad habitat for a given group when the available foraging arena size drops to 10% or below (Christensen et al., 2014)

3.3.1.1 *Fleet dynamics*

Fishing intensity in Ecospace is inherited from the base intensity specified in Ecopath, and its temporal fluctuations in Ecosim, and is expressed as a spatial distribution of effort for each fishing fleet in the model. Fishing effort is distributed across the Ecospace grid based on a simple economic evaluation, which balances the financial returns of catching target groups and their market value, against combined fixed fishing costs and catch per unit of effort (CPUE).

Ecospace offers four mechanisms to control fishing effort, per fleet, and its spatial distribution (de Mutsert et al. 2024):

- The total amount of Ecospace fishing effort can be increased or decreased through a fishing effort multiplier.
- Habitats can be used to prohibit fishing for specific fishing gear types over unsuitable bottom types.
- No-fishing zones (generally referred to as a Marine Protected Area or MPA) can be established to close specific cells to specific fishing gear types, too (Walters et al., 2000) at given times.
- The CPUE component of the economic evaluation can be affected by entering a distribution of relative fishing costs across the spatial grid, making specific map areas more expensive for fishing than others (Bauer et al., 2018; Walters et al., 1999). Although typically used to incorporate distance from port as an economic evaluation factor, this mechanism can also receive inverted historical fishing effort distributions to coax Ecospace to mimic observed fishing patterns within the constraints of the regular fishing effort gravity model, which may be conditioned on more than distance to port considerations.

The Ecospace model features a rudimentary advection module (akin to Pelets-2D, Callies, 2021) that has been used to model larval drift and assess MPA connectivity.

4 EwE UPDATES UNDER MARINEPLAN

Throughout MarinePlan EII has been making fixes and code changes to the EwE software. A few key contributions from MarinePlan include:

- November 2022: Made the fishing fleet costing structure time-dynamic
- January 2023: Improved display and internal handling of time series data
- January 2023: Improved memory usage of wind velocity fields

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.18111 Beta (11 January 2023).

- January 2023: EcoSampler correctly works with resampled diets
- February 2023: Prevent Windows from restarting when EwE is running long simulations
- February 2023: Catchabilities moved to new time series

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.18236 Beta (13 February 2023).

- March 2023: Added effort zone maps and cell area maps to Ecospace
- April 2023: Sped up Ecospace migration calculations
- May 2023: Added vulnerabilities cap to stabilize Ecospace
- July 2023: Added Ecosim diagnostics by trophic level

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.18413 Beta (17 July 2023).

- July 2023: Sped up Ecospace foraging capacity calculations
- August 2023: Debugged Ecospace catch accounting
- September 2023: Applied vulnerabilities cap to advanced fitting routines
- September 2023: Correctly account for excluded cells in EcoInd calculations
- October 2023: Removed shared arenas logic
- November 2023: Added the ability to import and export taxonomy

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.18597 Beta (21 December 2023).

- January 2024: Debugged extraction of Ecospace regional averages
- January 2024: Fixed 'sticky' forced Fs in Ecosim
- January 2024: Added bycatch penalties for Ecospace effort distribution
- February 2024: Debugged MPA Dynamics plug-in
- March 2024: Fixed external data / effort distribution order problem
- April 2024: Added Ecopath statistics auto-writing to disk

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.18865 Beta (EwE40 edition; 30 May 2024).

- May 2024: Improved utility of MPA Dynamics plug-in
- September 2024: Make plug-in handling more robust and secure

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.18910 Beta (8 September 2024)

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D1.1 OPERATIONAL EB-MSP FRAMEWORK AND GUIDANCE FOR PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

- October 2024: Fixed Ecospace MPA reordering bug
- November 2024: Fixed database update issue with non-US number formatting
- January 2025: Made Ecospace external map reading more robust to missing data values
- February 2025: Ecospace regions can now be altered through external maps
- February 2025: EwE can now work with model databases on cloud storage
- March 2025: Fixed Ecosim catch reporting bug when forced with fishing mortalities

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.19264 Beta (20 March 2025)

- March 2025: Added localizable units to environmental response functions
- April 2025: Fixed possible directory ambiguity in loading Ecospace external maps
- April 2025: Debugged application close pathways to always save pending changes
- April 2025: Fixed possible Ecospace external data connection mix-up bug
- May 2025: Fixed incorrect handling of ASCII NoData values in Ecospace external maps

These changes were included in release EwE 6.7.0.19431 Beta (19 May 2025)

5 DISCUSSION

Maintaining and expanding scientific software under the achievement-driven academic funding model is a challenge. The EwE software has an estimated 10.000 users worldwide in Academia, Non-Governmental Organizations and Industry, but as a free and open-source approach it mostly relies on occasional maintenance opportunities provided through (EU) project funding to stay relevant in an ever-changing computing landscape.

EII wishes to express their gratitude to the MarinePlan project for providing a lifeline for the EwE approach for the first 30 months of the project.

5.1 EwE RELEASE POLICY UNDER MARINEPLAN

Although this deliverable was due in March 2025, it is near impossible to define when the EwE software, that is perpetually under maintenance and development, would be feature complete for MarinePlan. EII delayed this deliverable to include a number of essential fixes to Ecospace which were deemed essential for the Western Mediterranean Planning Site. As such, the delivery date for this deliverable was set to EwE version 6.7.0.19431 Beta, on 19 May 2025.

Please note that EwE 6.7.0.19431 is still a beta release; pending software changes implemented through other channels and thorough community testing are needed before EwE version 6.7 can be released in full. Support of the MarinePlan projects has been acknowledged.

5.2 EwE CONNECTION WITH PELETS-2D

Although a direct link between the PELETS-2D (Callies, 2021) and Ecospace code was foreseen in the MarinePlan grant agreement to drive larval dispersal, close examination of the two software systems showed that this was a near-impossible to make the two software systems interoperate within the duration and the financial constraints of the MarinePlan project. Differences in data domain and model runtimes would also make a direct coupling of the two systems impractical.

As Ecospace only requires current fields that do not need to feed back into a current model, the PELETS-2D team delivered time-varying maps of current fields for direct ingestion into Ecospace via the Spatial Temporal Data Framework (Steenbeek et al., 2013). With these externally computed current fields, Ecospace can still implement PELETS-2D-driven larval dispersal.

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